

Maintenance of proper energy balance during transition period in dairy animals for improved performances

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Introduction

Energy balance may be understood as the balance between energy intake by the animals in form of food or any external source and the energy lost through various physiological mechanisms including digestion, activities, etc. If this energy balance goes negative due to more energy expenditure than energy intake, the animals' production, reproduction, health, behavior and other performances get adversely affected. On the other hand, if this energy balances in on higher side, the animals may become over conditioned (fat) which is also not desired. Both under conditioning and over conditioning i.e., deposition of energy reserves in the body (majorly deposited fat) of dairy animals resulted in poor and compromised production, reproduction and health performances. The maintenance of proper energy balance in dairy animals during per parturition time and initial lactation period becomes more important as there is dramatic change in demand of energy and nutrients in animals' body. Furthermore, animals show a high decline in feed consumption during per parturition time and initial lactation period which elevates imbalance in energy balance thus, cause negative energy balance in dairy animals. Hence, proper management practices should be practiced which helps in maintaining energy balance may reduce decline in performance of dairy animals.

With advancement in animal science practices including improved germplasm, breeding, and nutrition and management practices has boosted production reproduction, health, behavior and other performances of dairy animals. However, special attention needs to be paid during transition period wherein animals are exposed to several metabolic, physiological, and

environmental challenges. This article discusses changes in animals during per parturition and initial lactation period and associated management practices which help in overcoming the problems which arises due to imbalance in energy balance of animals.

Major changes in dairy animals' during per parturition and initial lactation period

More than two third growth and development of fetus occur during last tri-mester of gestation of animals. Therefore, animals require high plane of nutrition during this period. However, due to tremendous shift in hormonal profile of animals, their feed consumption highly declines. This further elevates imbalance in energy balance in dairy animals which needs to be checked through proper management practices. This imbalance in energy balance has far reaching effects on health and performances of dairy animals in ensuing lactation period. Herein, body reserves of animals are utilized for fetus growth, body maintenance, preparation for milk production in the ensuing lactation period. If the animals gain too much body reserves during pre-parturition period, the animals become more exposed to ailments such as displaced fetus, retained placenta, further decline in dry matter consumption occurs in dairy animals and hence they are pushed more in negative balance which ultimately leads to poor performances of health, production, reproduction and behaviors. Decrease of about 10-30% in dry matter consumption may be observed in dairy cows during transition period.

Assessment of body energy reserves in dairy animals

A careful watch over changes in the body reserves of dairy animals is a recommended practice. It aids in planned management conditions through which high losses of health, production and economics may be avoided. Body condition scores (BCS) is considered as an applicable and practicably adoptable method of assessing energy balance in dairy animals. Other methods include blood plasma profiling, ultrasound techniques and slaughtering of animals which may not be always is practicably feasible. BCS has been found correlated with growth, production, reproduction and health performances of animals. There may be several scales of BCS measurements however; commonly used BCS scale is 1 to 5 or 1 to 6 wherein, 1 represents emaciated or poorly conditioned and 5 or 6 represents high fatty or over conditioned conditions. Several body points such as vertebral column, transverse process, shelf formation in gaunt region, depression between hook bone, pin bone, prominence of ribs and bony prominence of animals are checked for fat deposition in animals. Both under and over-conditioned animals show poor

performances hence, these situations should be managed with proper husbandry practices such as improved nutrition, managing environment condition for animals.

Improved nutrition management

Supplemental Fat

Since, considerable amount of fat along with other constituents are found in the milk hence these nutrients should be additionally provided during peri-parturition period and initial lactation period to dairy animals. For this, supplementation of vegetable oils may be done for eg. Mustard oil, palm oil, soybean oil, etc. @ 100-200 ml per day depending upon body weight from 250 to 500 kg depending upon different breeds and species of gestating animals.

Herbal supplements

Due to highly changing or imbalanced metabolic and physiological conditions, animals suffer due to reactive oxygen species, free radicals and animals become susceptible towards invading pathogens. The immunity levels of animals become compromised and hence the supplementation of substances which have anti-oxidants, free radical scavenging, antimicrobial properties may be beneficial in such periods. Recent studies showed that supplementation of herbal mixture during transition period showed improved performance in animals. Supplementation of herbal mixture improves nutrient intake and availability which ultimately improves energy balance of dairy animals. Supplementation of *Asparagus racemosus* @100 to 200mg/kg body weight 2 months prepartum to 3 months postpartum period showed an improved reproductive performance. Koujalagi *et al.* (2018) showed improved oxidative stress and blood parameters in dairy cows when supplemented with herbal choline. Barjibhe *et al.* (2019) investigated that polyherbal mixture containing mustard oil, multi herbal mixture and butyric acid, reflected improved reproductive efficiency when supplemented during transition period.

Feeding regime and essential mineral and vitamin supplementation

Proper nutritional management is one of the major key to success in dairy farming. Recommended water quality and quantity should be provided *ad lib* to animals. Always provide balanced diet to animals along with important minerals such as zinc, selenium, manganese, copper, etc and necessary vitamins like vitamin A, E, C may be supplemented to animals. The above listed minerals and vitamins have anti-oxidant and immunity modulating effects in animals' body.

Housing and handling management for dairy animals

Temperature inside animals' house should be managed that it is around 18-25 degree centigrade. This temperature range offers proper thermal comfort to dairy animals. During summer season mechanical fans, foggers, mister or wallowing facilities may improve thermal comfort for dairy animals. During cold weather conditions double, layered sheets may be put around open areas near dairy farms. These methods prevent animals expending unwanted energy in maintaining body temperature and stays away from going into negative energy balance. In addition to this, proper ventilation facilities should be provided in house of animals. Animals should be provided with proper bedding materials of about 15cm thickness and should be replaced on regular intervals to ensure proper dryness and grip. Animals should be gently handled and no use of harsh methods may be followed at house premises.

Conclusions

It may be concluded that imbalanced energy balance in dairy animals' weather negative or over conditioned should be avoided as these conditions lead to compromised immunity status and hence, poor health, production and economics of dairy farm. Nonetheless, advancement in animal science practices including improved germplasm, breeding, and nutrition and management practices may boost production, reproduction, health, behavior and other performances of dairy animals. Dairy farmers should adopt such practices which uniformly maintain dry matter intake and reduces the chance of negative energy balance in dairy animals for enhancement in overall Performa.